

D3.1

Report on the historical construction of the corpus

Document Identifier

→D3.1 Report on the historical
construction of the corpus

Date Due

→M18

Submission Date

→27 October 2020

Work Package 3

→ Images and materiality in Islam

Lead Beneficiary

→CNRS

This project has received
the European union's
Horizon 2020 research and
innovation programme under
the Marie Skłodowska-Curie
grant agreement N°813547.

ITN-MIDA 813547

By:

Robin Cognée (ESR7),
Mahdieh Tavakol (ESR 8),
and Elaheh Habibi (ESR 9)

Supervisor:

Prof. Mercedes Volait (CNRS)

Introduction

A material corpus is not a loose or random grouping of artefacts or objects, rather is a historically shaped ensemble that can reflect the intentions, concerns, and biases of the agents involved in the formation of that corpus.

Moreover, these historically-shaped corpora come to be studied and researched by a scholar along with specific criteria and objectives, whether she/he tries to reconstitute a disappeared endowed library, study the processing and impact of war pictures, or retrace the architectural history of Islamic places of worship.

The purpose of this report is to follow the historical construction of the three material corpora under study by the three ESRs, Robin Cognée (ESR 7), Mahdieh Tavakol (ESR 8), and Elaheh Habibi (ESR 9).

Part 1.

Mosque architecture and scripture in Bosnia and Herzegovina: between tradition and modernity

The main corpus that ESR7 uses in his research is a mosque database compiled since 2016 by the researcher, identifying all the mosques in Bosnia and Herzegovina (hereafter BiH) built prior to and after the war of 1992-1995, going back to the Austro-Hungarian administration of the region (1878-1918). The database consists of raw data material such as localization, dates of (re)construction, destruction, restoration, and renovation, and so on. The researcher has used many sources of different types to constitute this database, including local monographs, architectural publications, and books, archives or international reports. The database emanates from different backgrounds, mainly from the Islamic Community (Islamska zajednica, hereafter IZ), and the Islamic authorities of the Bosnian Muslims (from 1918 to 1991, more broadly, of all the Yugoslav Muslims). The latter is naturally the most able organisation to provide a vast amount of information concerning the Bosnian mosques.

The mass of data collected in IZ-affiliated sources, although transparent and valuable, has to be cross-checked and complemented with information drawn from non-IZ sources, with more descriptive details (architectural features, materials or visual appearance). This information can be obtained through fieldwork and additional data and photo collecting to get a complete and objective overall picture, not only drawn out on statistics and dates. The final objective is to highlight the architectural and scriptural changes in Bosnian mosque architecture throughout history, and to study their impact aesthetically, religiously, socially, or politically in the Bosnian society.

One has to remember the different positioning and statuses of the IZ since its creation in 1882, from its difficult cohabitation with the Austro-Hungarian authorities to its active (and calculating) compliance with the Titist Yugoslav regime, under which the IZ became the main promotor of

the Bosniak/Muslim emerging nationality.¹

Finally, the IZ post-war symbiosis with Bosniak nationalism and renewed identity is a contemporary background that cannot and must not be occulted when addressing the issue of mosques in the country. The different historical phases of destructions and (re) constructions of the Bosnian mosques over the past 140 years, as well as the architectural and scriptural changes affecting them, have been highly reflecting the history and politics of the IZ, as well as the political and religious contexts of the time, and, naturally, the socio-religious dynamics of the Bosnian Muslim community.

Therefore, if the IZ provides many data, it is not exempted from various omissions, discrepancies, and biases. These may appear between local IZ-affiliated scholars and IZ sources (archives and periodicals), all the more given the fact that boundaries between these two can often be blurred. Another weakness is the

fact that the data on mosques have never been adequately centralized (or at least organized and classified) by the IZ and is scattered among the different local (congregational) archives, publications, and authors. Related to that, it turned out that there is, for a certain number of mosques, a lack of information, either because they have been un(der)documented or historically/architecturally less remarkable. Indeed some gaps appear regarding the amount of data that are likely to come out from one mosque to another.

¹ « Muslim in the national sense », as described in the Yugoslav censuses since 1971.

Part 2.

The Life Journey of a Safavid Personal Library: The Library of Bahā' al-Dīn Muḥammad al-Āmilī (1547-1621)

The corpus, which is the focus of the research by ESR8 is the manuscripts belonging to the library of the great scholar of the early 17th century Persia, Baha al-Din Muhammad al-Amili, or Sheykh Bahai'. Upon his death, Sheykh Bahai had endowed his library to the shrine of Ali ibn Musa al-Rida, in Mashhad, Iran. His library, however, does not exist today as a specified physical collection and its individual manuscripts are scattered in the libraries within Iran and beyond. This means that this once-existent corpus of books is now dissolved in other collections and has lost its identity as an independent collection. The current work of ESR8 focuses on reconstructing the library (and, thus, to re-build the corpus) by identifying and collecting the manuscripts once belonging to the Sheykh.

In this way, so far, she has come up with a corpus consisting of more than 100 manuscripts sitting in some 20 libraries. A large portion of this corpus (some 40 MSs), resting in the Astan Quds library in Mashhad, consists of a) the Sheykh's manuscripts that have been sitting in that library since their endowment in 1621 CE, b) the Sheykh's manuscripts that had remained in his city of residence (Isfahan) and were endowed to the Mashhad shrine some 130 years after his death by Nadir Shah (1688-1747), and c) his originally endowed manuscripts which had come out of the library and circulated between different collections over centuries and were re-endowed to the Astan Quds only in the past few decades. A second large portion of the Sheykh's MSs (more than 30) are in Tehran's important libraries, including the libraries of Majlis, Malek, Sepahsalar, Tehran University and the National Library. These manuscripts usually belonged to the private collations of politicians, scholars or businessmen, whose collections were either endowed

or sold to these public libraries after their deaths in the 20th century. Of this corpus, ten manuscripts are in Qom. The rest of the corpus includes some 20 individual manuscripts that are kept in the libraries in smaller towns in Iran, as well as at Princeton, Jerusalem, Lucknow, Najaf, and Dublin. These manuscripts of Sheykh Bahai', therefore, have been shifting their legal status between private and public ownership over centuries.

The next step in this research would be to track the stories behind these manuscript's movements and circulation. The aim would be to re-contextualise these manuscripts and do research on their provenance to begin understanding the processes that have led to their reconfiguration and the new meanings that have been ascribed to them in their new contexts.

Part 3.

“Photography of War in Iran (1980-2019): Past Inspirations and Current Revisions”

One of the primary documents that are being used by ESR9 in her research “Photography of War in Iran (1980-2019): Past Inspirations and Current Revisions” is a photo book (album) held currently at the National Library of France (BnF) in Paris. Widely considered to be the first and the most important photo exhibition of the time, the book represents 147 works of different professional and amateur photographers taken during the first year of the Iran-Iraq war and exhibited at the Museum of Contemporary Art (TMOCA) in 1981. This photo album’s main fundamental characteristic is to represent a wide array of visual works by photographers on political spectrum. These photographs have been reproduced, reconfigured, and circulated later during and after the war in different ways both in Iran and outside Iran. The photographs help the researcher explore the circumstances that these photographs were produced and the extent to which the regime used them as propaganda. The current reception of these

photographs is examined in this research through the reproduction and circulation of the same photographs on online platforms such as Instagram and Telegram and what they signify about changing subjectivities.

Called Images: the Islamic Revolution of Iran, this photo book was published in 1981 by the Iranian Ministry of Islamic Guidance in Tehran in cooperation with the Tehran Museum of Contemporary Art (TMOCA). The book represents the first significant art exhibitions held after the Islamic Republic’s formation in 1980, dedicated solely to revolution and war photography. The presence of about 75 professional and amateur photographers turned this exhibition into a rare collective photo exhibition of its time.

The occurrence of revolution and the following war had considerable influence on the content, the style, and tone of this photo book. The preface of the book and the captions of photographs are written

in English targeting western audience. One can distinguish two different viewpoints that the document represents on the Iranian revolution and the Iran-Iraq war. The first viewpoint is the viewpoint of the author/s on “the great Revolution and its people” which it claimed to be the viewpoint of the Iranian people. The other viewpoint is the one that the author/s seek to criticize. As mentioned by the author/s, the book is curated to rectify “misunderstanding and the ill-intendedness of the imperialist media in relationship to this great Revolution and its people” (3). The photographs are selected in favor of a particular narrative and interpretation; each photograph is captioned with long sentences, formulating a narrative which later became the dominant narrative of war and revolution in the Islamic Republic of Iran. Origin and ownership of all of the photographs are indicated in the book. However, in the interviews conducted by the researcher, some of the photographers claimed that they have not been involved in the process of the curation and captioning

of the book. Instead, the book was curated by the head of the photography department of TMOCA of the time. It is also unclear if the book is published in Tehran or in Berlin, where another famous Iran war photo book, “The Imposed War” was published in 1981.

The life history of these photographs is as diverse as their creators. As the war brought insecurity and vulnerability to people who lived through it, it created an unstable situation for these photographs and their preservation over time. Some of the photographs are saved in private collections, some became part of the archive of photo agencies like Magnum photo in Paris and New York, and some stayed in Iran within the state archives of revolution and war, or in the archives of the newspapers.

Conclusion

It is worth mentioning that a double subjectivity is inevitably implied when it comes to the study of historical corpora: one owing to the (often) multiple contingencies, actors, and contexts along which the corpus has been historically shaped, and the other attached to the intentions, concerns and the biases of the scholar who studies the corpus. The former may have brought discrepancies, biases, omissions and sometimes manipulations regarding the constitution of the corpus. The latter impacts the research itself: studying corpora is not indeed an objective and neutral process.

Awareness of this double subjectivity must be employed precisely to address the issue of potential corpus biases, using informed criticism, respecting research ethics, privileging scientific knowledge and outcomes.

The history of the library of Bahā' al-Dīn Muḥammad al-Āmilī reflects a story of dispersion and dissolution. The library has lost its identity as its individual manuscripts have been dispersed, circulating between a variety of public and private collections over the past four centuries. As a result, these manuscripts' legal status has

constantly been changing between personal and public (endowed) ownership. Although the owner of the collections that hosted Sheykh Bahai' belongings usually cherished the fact that their collections held those items, they did not try to separate those items from other objects in their collections. The manuscripts once belonging to Sheykh's library, thus, have been dissolved and re-contextualised in pools of manuscripts that collectors from different walks of the society gathered together. While the work of ESR 8 so far has been focused on identifying the many present collections holding Sheykh Bahai' dispersed manuscripts, the intentions, biases and concerns of these collectors are something to be researched in the next stages of the research.

The war pictures taken during the Iran-Iraq conflict of 1980-1988 have been published in various media and countries, serving different goals, purposes and even sometimes ideologies. Choosing which ones should be enlightened and studied, why, where, when, is up to the researcher and the objective of her analysis.

Conclusion

The corpus constituted by the Bosnian mosques is a neutral one, the data related to these mosques is not. Therefore, addressing the numbers, characteristics, features (etc.) of these mosques is dependent on the sources – many of them religious and/or non-academic – which contain this data. Treating and exploiting the data implies potential omissions, errors and certainly choices (dismissing one piece of data over another, for instance) on the part of the researcher that may be avoided or reduced to the minimum through a thorough cross-referencing and checking of data and sources.